

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS OF TRAINING OF SPECIALTY SUBJECTS ON THE BASIS OF TRAINING SIMULATORS

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Annotation: The great importance is the fact that professors, teachers operating in the educational system, know how to use simulators in the educational process from the Internet system along with rapidly developing information technology and modern computers. One of the important factors in carrying out this on the example of the science of success power supply is the need to use statistical and experimental testing techniques in the creation of software-that is, simulators on educational subjects taught in educational institutions.

Keywords: Simulator, statistical method, self-education, experiment testing, power supply.

In the technical directions of higher education institutions, the use of information technologies in the lectures, practical and laboratory sessions of general professional and specialty Sciences is carried out somewhat slowly. As a factor of the perfect prolongation of students in general professional and specialty disciplines, it is possible to demonstrate that the courses are provided with all types of educational literature and that there is a material and technical base that provides the formation of practical conics, the use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the conditions created for Independent Education, the Taking into account the above mentioned, the practical support of the Department of "fundamentals of power supply" of Tashkent State Technical University in the context of "Electroenergetics" of Karakalpak State University and the educational plan of electric power generation (energy production, transmission and taqsimlash) there is an electronic textbook on the subject of "fundamentals of power supply", which is included in the block of general The electronic textbook is provided with a text of lectures, readings and educational uses for independent study. The level of visibility of the textbook was created using computer technologies 2D and implemented using 3D-format animasion models. Laboratory work Electronics Workbench, Rapid SCADA softwareeksi, MatLab Simulink 2014 Software Engineering, Hybrid Type Stand Alone 3kW 48V 200AH specially

designed simulation software for PV system (Solarius-PV Software) and x.k. prepared on the type of assignments based on the capabilities.

In order to determine the effectiveness achieved in the application of the electronic textbook in the educational process, one lecture and two laboratory works with a moderate level of complexity were selected in the experimental and control groups of Tashkent State Technical University and Karakalpak State University.

Experimental-testing work was carried out in three stages: diagnostic (prognostic), organizational preparation, practical and generalizing stages. With the help of the mathematical statistical method of predicting the objectivity of the results of experimental - test works, the effectiveness of the proposed method, the indicators of observation and experimental-test works were determined. In the control of students' knowledge, test tests, written work, oral question and answer techniques were used.

At the end of the experimental work, the factors affecting the mustahil creative thinking of the students in the experimental group, the student's knowledge, qualifications, skills, were determined. The total result of the quantitative analysis is presented in the table and in the picture. From the table, the ratio between the quality indicators of the experimental and control groups was equal to 1,064.

Number of students (who have achieved this assessment)	4	5			4	5		
The average arithmetic value of the odds	$X_t=3,46$				$X_n=3,25$			
Coefficient	$\eta = X_m / X_H = 1,064$							

Picture. Quantitative analysis diagram. We can conclude from this that the result of the experimental group turned out to be better in comparison with the control group. This means that the participants in the experimental groups found their proof as a result of the experimental-testing work that the power supply basics science lectures and laboratory exercises could perform well with the help of training simulators, software.

USED LITERATURES:

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